

Manuscript Number:

Title: Modeling Grinding Kinetics of Fat Based Anhydrous Pastes

Article Type: Research Article

Keywords: hazelnut and cocoa paste; Casson model; population balance model; Kapur constants; G-H model; packing volume fraction

Corresponding Author: Dr. Marcello Fidaleo,

Corresponding Author's Institution:

First Author: Nicoletta A Miele

Order of Authors: Nicoletta A Miele; Angela Borriello; Marcello Fidaleo; Paolo Masi; Silvana Cavella

Abstract: The objective of this research was to study the kinetics of grinding of an anhydrous paste based on hazelnut and cocoa, in stirred ball mills by means of particles size determination and rheological analysis. Grinding was carried out in a pilot refiner (30 °C, 72 rpm, 60 kg of 5.5-mm diameter stainless steel balls) with 10 kg of paste. The grinding kinetics was described in terms of the cumulative oversize fraction by the second order solution of the population balance model allowing the estimation of the first and the second Kapur constants as a function of particle size class. The flow curves of refined pastes were successfully modeled with the Casson rheological model and can be explained by the theory of dense suspensions. Further studies are however necessary to develop a model for the description of the rheological behavior as a function of solid packing fraction and shear rate.

Highlights

- A population balance approach proved adequate to model grinding kinetics
- The first and second Kapur constants were estimated and regressed on size class
- Casson model describes the pseudoplastic behavior of the refining paste
- The packing fraction of the refining paste was related to its rheological behavior
- Grinding affected mainly the rheology of the pastes

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23

TITLE

Modeling Grinding Kinetics of Fat Based Anhydrous Pastes

AUTHORS

^{1,2}Nicoletta A. Miele, ¹Angela Borriello, ³Marcello Fidaleo ¹, ^{1,2}Paolo Masi, ^{1,2}Silvana Cavella

AFFILIATIONS

¹Department of Agricultural Sciences -University of Naples Federico II, 80055 Portici, Italy

²Center of Food Innovation and Development in the Food Industry, University of Naples Federico II, 80055 Portici, Italy

³Department for Innovation in Biological, Agro-food and Forest systems, University of Tuscia, 01100 Viterbo, Italy

Keywords: hazelnut and cocoa paste; Casson model; population balance model; Kapur constants; G-H model; packing volume fraction.

¹Corresponding Author: email fidaleom@unitus.it; tel. +39 0761357421; Fax +39 0761357498. Department for Innovation in Biological, Agro-food and Forest systems, University of Tuscia, Via S. Camillo de Lellis, snc, 01100 Viterbo, Italy.

24 *Abstract*

25 The objective of this research was to study the kinetics of grinding of an anhydrous paste
26 based on hazelnut and cocoa, in stirred ball mills by means of particles size determination
27 and rheological analysis. Grinding was carried out in a pilot refiner (30 °C, 72 rpm, 60 kg
28 of 5.5-mm diameter stainless steel balls) with 10 kg of paste. The grinding kinetics was
29 described in terms of the cumulative oversize fraction by the second order solution of the
30 population balance model allowing the estimation of the first and the second Kapur
31 constants as a function of particle size class.

32 The flow curves of refined pastes were successfully modeled with the Casson
33 rheological model and can be explained by the theory of dense suspensions. Further studies
34 are however necessary to develop a model for the description of the rheological behavior
35 as a function of solid packing fraction and shear rate.

36

37

38 **Introduction**

39 Fat based anhydrous pastes used for the preparation of ice creams are close to nut based
40 spreads for the recipe, but they are not spreadable across a wide temperature range and
41 become more flowable than a spread at 20-25 °C (Birkett, 2009). They could also resemble
42 a filling cream, that is generally fat and sugar based, and represents an important
43 component in different confectionary foods, in which provides taste, texture and adhesion
44 of the baked items (Miele et al., 2015).

45 Cream processing requires a solid particle size reduction operation, called refining
46 and/or grinding. Its main goal is to obtain a desired solid particle size, specific for each
47 product. During grinding, the tailings of large particles absorb part of the mechanical
48 energy, causing an increase in surface energy and a decrease in particle size. A limit
49 condition is reached when the finest particles agglomerate and release part of surface
50 energy, greatly reducing the grinding efficiency (Li et al., 2017). Another quality attribute
51 of the refined paste is its viscosity which is affected by grinding. Excessive grinding results
52 in higher viscosity of the paste and may require the addition of expensive viscosity
53 modifiers and/or dispersant phase to adjust its value to the target for the specific
54 application.

55 Very few studies have dealt so far with food refining by means of stirred ball mills
56 (Alamprese et al., 2007; Lucisano et al., 2006; Hennart et al., 2012; Fidaleo et al. 2017a;
57 Fidaleo et al., 2017b) and even fewer studies have focused on modeling aspects. In
58 particular, Fidaleo et al. (2017b) developed a mathematical model of refining of a hazelnut
59 and cocoa based anhydrous paste in stirred ball mills. The model was able to predict the
60 effect of key parameters - grinding media diameter and mass, rotation speed, recycle flow
61 rate and temperature - on the refining kinetics, determined by the fineness of the paste as
62 measured by a digital micrometer, at different process scales.

63 Thus, considering the lack of scientific knowledge on the modeling of food refining in
64 stirred ball mills, the objective of this research was to study the kinetics of grinding of an
65 anhydrous paste based on hazelnut and cocoa, in stirred ball mills by means of particles
66 size determination and rheological analysis.

67

68 **2. Theoretical aspects**

69 The kinetics of batch grinding can be described by using the population balance model
 70 that considers the change in the quantity of particles in each size class as a function of the
 71 grinding time (Varinot, Berthiaux, & Dodds, 1999). It corresponds to the following set of
 72 differential equations of mass balance over discrete size intervals:

$$\frac{dm_i(t)}{dt} = -S_i m_i(t) + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} S_j b_{ij} m_j(t) \quad (1)$$

73 where t is the grinding time; i is the size index (varies between 1, smaller class size, and n ,
 74 larger class size), m_i is the mass fraction of particles bounded by size-indexes $i-1$ and i (for
 75 example, particles passing and retained on two adjacent sieves in a standard mesh series);
 76 the selection function S_i is the rate of grinding of the i -th class of particles; the breakage
 77 function b_{ij} is the fraction of daughter particles of i -th size when j -th size particles are
 78 broken.

79 Eq. (1) can also be written in cumulative form as:

$$\frac{dR_i(t)}{dt} = -S_i R_i(t) + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} R_j(t) [S_{j+1} B_{ij+1} - S_j B_{ij}] \quad (2)$$

80 where $B_{ij} = \sum_{k=i+1}^n b_{kj}$ is the cumulative breakage function representing the probability of
 81 fragments from a particle of size x_j to have a size less than x_i and $R_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^i m_j(t)$ is
 82 the mass fraction of particles greater than x_i .

83 Use of Eq.s (2) requires knowledge of the functions B_{ij} and S_i which are all the more
 84 difficult to obtain the higher the precision required, as this implies a larger number of
 85 classes (Berthiaux et al., 1996). It has been shown (Kapur and Agarwal, 1970) that Eq.s (2)
 86 admit the following approximate solutions, the so called G-H solutions:

$$R_i(t) = R_i(0) \exp\left(k_i^{(1)} t + k_i^{(2)} \frac{t^2}{2!}\right) \quad (3)$$

87 where $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}$ are lamped parameters called the first and the second Kapur constant,
 88 also indicated with G_i and H_i , respectively. These equations can be easily applied to

89 experimental results to simulate $R_i(t)$ for each class of size x_i of particles. In fact, compared
 90 to Eq.s (2), they contain only two unknown parameters, $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}$, which can be easily
 91 computed from a limited amount of experimental data. The main drawback of Eq.s (3) is
 92 that $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}$ do not have a direct physical meaning while S_i and b_{ij} or S_i and B_{ij} in Eq.s
 93 (1) or (2), respectively, do. This is probably the reason why many studies, such as (Hennart
 94 et al., 2012) used the first order approximation of Eq. (3) (where $k_i^{(2)}$ is assumed to be
 95 zero) for grinding kinetics modeling. In fact, under this circumstance, $k_i^{(1)}$ corresponds to
 96 S_i , the selection function, from which the breakage function can be calculated as $b_{ij}=(S_{i-1}-$
 97 $S_i)/S_j$ (Hennart et al., 2012; Berthiaux et al., 1996). In any case, it has been shown that even
 98 from $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}$ values estimated by using Eq.s (3), it is possible to back calculate
 99 breakage functions (Purker, Agrawal, & Kapur, 1986).

100 By fitting Eq.s (3) to the R_i -vs- t experimental data, both $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}$ values can be
 101 estimated for each size class x_i . Several equations have been proposed to represent $k_i^{(1)}$ as a
 102 function of the particle size x_i . In this work we used the following functional form
 103 (Varinot et al., 1999) to express both $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}$ dependence on x_i :

$$k_i^{(j)} = \frac{kx_i^\alpha}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{x_i}{x^*}\right)^\Lambda\right]} \quad (4)$$

104 where k , α , x^* and Λ are fitting parameters while j indicate the first ($j=1$) or the second
 105 ($j=2$) Kapur constant.

106 For $x_i \ll x^*$, assuming $\Lambda > 0$, Eq. (4) reduces to another equation that has been proposed
 107 to express $k_i^{(1)}$ as a function of x_i (Berthiaux et al., 1996; Hennart et al., 2012):

$$k_i^{(j)} = kx_i^\alpha \quad (5)$$

108 As far as flow rheological properties, an anhydrous paste can be considered a dispersion
 109 where cocoa, sugar, nut and milk solids are dispersed in a liquid phase made up of oil and
 110 nut and cocoa fats. Its flow behavior can be associated to that of food suspensions (Servais
 111 et al., 2002). The Cross, Carreau and Quemada-Casson models have been used to describe

112 the rheological data of apparent viscosity as a function of shear rate for many food
113 dispersions (Rao, 2007).

114 The Quemada model (Fang et al., 1997) is a viscosity equation for dispersed systems
115 based on zero-shear, η_0 , and infinite-shear, η_∞ , viscosities, and a structural parameter λ
116 dependent on the shear rate. For highly concentrated dispersed systems η_∞ is generally
117 much lower than η_0 , so that $\eta_\infty/\eta_0 \ll 1$ and the dispersion may have a yield stress. Under
118 this circumstance the Quemada model reduces to the Casson model:

$$\eta^{1/2} = \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{\dot{\gamma}} \right)^{1/2} + (\eta_\infty)^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

119 where σ_0 is the Casson yield stress and η_∞ is the infinite-shear viscosity, also called the
120 Casson plastic viscosity.

121 The relative viscosity of a concentrated solid suspension can be related to its solid
122 volume fraction (ϕ) through equations of the form of Krieger and Dougherty's equation,
123 originally proposed for rigid sphere suspensions (Wildemuth and Williams, 1984):

$$\eta_r = \frac{\eta}{\eta_s} = \left(1 - \frac{\phi}{\phi_m} \right)^{-[\eta]\phi_m} \quad (7)$$

124
125 where ϕ_m is the maximum packing volume fraction of the solids, η_r and η_s are the paste
126 reduced viscosity and the dispersant viscosity, respectively, and $[\eta]$ is the intrinsic
127 viscosity that can be assumed equal to 2.5 if the particles or build-up aggregates are
128 spherical.

129 The a priori prediction of the maximum packing fraction, ϕ_m , for a system of particles
130 depends on its geometric arrangement. Suspensions of monomodal spheres self-assemble
131 to form a so-called random close-packed (RCP) arrangement with a ϕ_m of about 0.63
132 (McGear, 1961). For multimodal systems, it is more difficult to arrive at a theoretical value
133 of ϕ_m . Qualitatively, small spheres may fit into the spaces between packed large spheres
134 thus increasing ϕ_m , and according to Eq. (7), decreasing the viscosity of the suspension.
135 Rheological experiments with bimodal, multimodal, and polydisperse systems show that at

136 equal total particle volume fraction, the viscosities of multimodal systems are lower than
137 for their monodisperse counterparts.

138 3. Experimental

139 3.1 Materials

140 The following formulation with reference to 100 g of hazelnut and cocoa based
141 anhydrous paste was used: sugar (31 g), vegetable oils (27 g), ice sugar (14 g), cacao
142 powder (11 g), hazelnut paste (8 g), milk powder and derivatives (7.5 g), other (0.9 g),
143 lecithin (0.6 g) (Fidaleo et al., 2017b). The solids volume fraction of the product (volume
144 of solids divided by the volume of paste), ϕ , is an important material property of
145 suspensions since it is related to flow behavior. An approximation of ϕ can be obtained
146 from the mass of the main ingredients (m_i) and their density (ρ_i):

$$\phi = \frac{m_s/\rho_s + m_c/\rho_c + m_m/\rho_m + m_h/\rho_h}{m_s/\rho_s + m_c/\rho_c + m_m/\rho_m + m_h/\rho_h + m_o/\rho_o + m_l/\rho_l + m_{oh}/\rho_{oh}} \quad (8)$$

147 where m_s is the sugar mass, m_c the cacao mass, m_m the milk solids mass, m_h the
148 hazelnut solids mass, m_l the lecithin mass, m_o the vegetable oil mass, m_{oh} the hazelnut oil
149 mass, while ρ_s , ρ_c , ρ_m , ρ_h , ρ_l , ρ_o and ρ_{oh} are the corresponding densities (Taylor et al., 2009;
150 van der Vaart et al., 2013). The densities of the materials at 20°C are as follows: sugar,
151 1426 kg/m³; cacao solids, 1350 kg/m³; lecithin, 893 kg/m³ (van der Vaart et al., 2013);
152 milk solids, 1480 kg/m³ (Berlin and Pallansch, 1963); hazelnut paste solids, 916 kg/m³
153 (Ozdemir and Akinici, 2004).; seed oil, 900 kg/m³. The hazelnut paste was assumed as
154 made up of 60% oil and 40% solids (Ozdemir and Akinici, 2004). The solids volume
155 fraction estimated by Eq. (8) was equal to 0.568, thus close to that of a typical milk
156 chocolate (with 30% w/w fat) of 0.575.

157

158 3.2 Sample preparation

159 For cream production, a stirred ball mill was used (model Micron 20, Selmi s.r.l,
160 Modena, Italy) with 60 kg of 5.5-mm diameter stainless steel balls. Ingredient weight was
161 set on 10 kg, according to manual specifications of the instrument. Speed rate was fixed
162 (72 rpm) and the temperature was controlled (30±2°C). The circulation of the product
163 during refinement was maintained by a dual-purpose volumetric pump. Sampling was
164 carried out from 0 to 120 min during the grinding process.

165 3.3 Particle size distribution

166 The particle size distribution (PDS) was analyzed by using a Mastersizer laser
167 diffraction particle size analyser equipped with Hydro 3000 dispersion unit (Malvern
168 Instruments, Worcestershire, UK) (Armini et al., 2018). For each cream, two different
169 replicates were analyzed and for each replicate, 15 measurements were performed.

170 The fineness of the pastes was also determined by using a digital micrometer (Fidaleo et
171 al., 2017b).

172 **3.4 Rheological properties**

173 Viscosity of cream samples, as well as that of the vegetable oil used and the supernatant
174 liquid obtained by centrifugation of the refined paste, was determined by a Modular
175 Advanced Rheometer System (Haake MARS, Thermo Scientific, Waltham, USA),
176 equipped with a vane tool geometry (diameter 22mm, length 16 mm, distance 8.5 mm).
177 The viscosity curves were measured as a function of increasing shear rate (0.01-100 s⁻¹) at
178 30°C. Three replications for each sample were performed.

179

180 **3.5 Determination of solid bed density and maximum packing fraction**

181 For solid bed density (SBD) determination, a known weight of samples (≈10 g) was
182 placed in 50-ml centrifuge tubes. The tubes were placed in a thermal oven (Universal
183 Oven, Memmert, Schwabach, Germany) at 30 °C for two hours before being centrifuged
184 at 10000 rpm for 20 minutes. The Solid bed density of the samples was calculated as the
185 ratio of the mass of solids in the suspension to the volume of solid bed after
186 centrifugation.

187 The maximum packing fraction (ϕ_m) was calculated by considering the PSD of each
188 paste as based on a mixture of spheres with n different diameters, D_i , and corresponding
189 volumetric fractions, X_i . For n-component mixtures of spheres, Lee (1970) proposed the
190 following equations:

$$(\phi_p)_i = \sum_{j=1}^{j=n} \phi_{ij} \cdot X_j \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{j=n} X_j = 1 \quad (10)$$

191 where:

192 - ϕ_p is a function that predicts ϕ_m ;

193 - i and j refers to the particles with diameter D_i and D_j , respectively;

194 -
$$\phi_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0.639 + \frac{\phi_{max}\left(\frac{D_i}{D_j}\right) - 0.639}{0.265}, & D_i \geq D_j \\ 0.639 + \frac{\phi_{max}\left(\frac{D_j}{D_i}\right) - 0.639}{0.735}, & D_i < D_j \end{cases}$$

195 - $\phi_{max}(D_i/D_j)$ is the maximum volume fraction of binary mixtures with diameter ratio
196 D_i/D_j .

197 The maximum volume fraction of binary mixtures as a function of diameter ratio,
198 $\phi_{max}(D_i/D_j)$, was calculated starting from the data reported in the paper of Lee (1970).
199 The data from Fig. 1 of the paper, labeled as corrected data series, were fitted by the
200 probit 4P nonlinear model implemented in JMP software (v. 14.2.0) and the obtained
201 regression equation was used to estimate the maximum volume fraction for a given
202 diameter ratio. The fitting was excellent with R^2 , RMSE and mean relative error equal to
203 0.998, 0.0038 and 0.34%, respectively. ϕ_m was then calculated as the smallest value of ϕ_p
204 determined by Eq. (9).

205 3.6 Data analysis

206 Several indexes of the PSD based on the volume of particles were estimated, including
207 the percentiles, D_{10} , D_{50} , and D_{90} , and the oversize fraction, R_i , that is the fraction of
208 particles having size greater than x_i , the lower limit of the particle size class i .

209 ANOVA and Fisher's method with $\alpha=5\%$ were applied on data to compare both PSD
210 parameters and fineness of pastes by using JMP statistical software release 14.2.0, (SAS
211 Institute, Cary, NC, USA). Where necessary, data were transformed (Box-Cox
212 transformations) to minimize variance differences among samples and submitted to
213 ANOVA.

214 The rheological data of viscosity as a function of shear rate were fitted by JMP
215 statistical software by using the weighed least squares method (with the inverse of squared
216 experimental viscosities as weights). The oversize as a function of time data, the Kapur
217 constants as a function of particle size data and the volumetric packing factor as a function
218 of diameter ratio for binary systems data were fitted by the least squares method by using
219 JMP software.

220 A Matlab (The MathWorks, Inc., MA, USA) script was developed to calculate ϕ_m
221 according to Eq. (9) and it was validated on four PSDs (rectangular, triangular, etc.)
222 described by Lee (1970).

223 3. Results and Discussion

224 3.1 Particle size distribution and fineness data

225 The PSD curves of anhydrous pastes as a function of grinding time are reported in Fig.
226 1. Before grinding ($t=0$ min), the paste presented a tri-modal PSD with particle sizes
227 ranging from 0.8 to about 800 μm . After 5 min of grinding ($t= 5$ min), the peak relative to
228 the larger particles became a shoulder, and after 20 min ($t= 20$ min) the distribution could
229 be considered almost unimodal, even if a left small shoulder, corresponding to particles
230 with sizes between 0.8 and 1.7 μm , was still observed in PSD curves.

231 Fig. 1

232

233 Table 1 reports the percentiles of the PSD and the fineness, as result of the micrometer
234 measurements, of paste during grinding. It can be observed that increasing the grinding
235 time resulted in a statistically significant negative effect on D_{90} and on the other
236 percentiles. D_{90} values highly correlated with micrometer readings, as reported in the
237 literature (Fidaleo et al., 2017). Pastes refined for 90 and 120 min were not statistically
238 different for fineness but were different for almost all the percentiles of PSD, even if the
239 differences were very small. However, after already 120 minute the average particle size
240 was around 16 μm , so it was not convenient to move on with the grinding process for this
241 type of product.

242

243 Table 1

244 Fig. 2 reports the oversize R_i as a function of grinding time for several size classes of
245 particles (only 10 size classes of 31 classes analyzed).

246

247 Fig. 2

248

249 The oversize fraction of particles of small size classes did not change much or tended to
250 stabilize as a function of time while for large size classes it dropped to zero after a small
251 grinding time. This behavior required to filter the R_i data before using them with Eq. (3).
252 R_i -vs- t data were fitted by using Eq. (3) to obtain $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}$ estimates for each size
253 class x_i , as reported in Fig. 3. For small size classes the estimated second Kapur
254 coefficients $k_i^{(1)}$ were not statistically different from zero, thus a first order model was

255 adequate to describe the data. For fittings of intermediate size classes, both $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}$
256 coefficients were statistically different from zero, so the second order model was necessary
257 to describe the data.

258 $k_i^{(1)}$ values were negative for all the size classes studied and increased in absolute
259 value as x_i increased. $k_i^{(2)}$ values were positive and increased with the size class. The ratio
260 between $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}/2!$ values for each size class x_i was about constant and equal to
261 314 ± 18 min.

262 In the literature, Eq. (4) was suggested to express the first Kapur constant, $k_i^{(1)}$ (Varinot et
263 al., 1999), but in the present work the same equation was also applied for $k_i^{(2)}$ data. The
264 estimated unknown parameters are reported in Table 2. Interestingly, α , x^* and Λ estimates
265 did not differ much between the first and the second Kapur function as could be expected
266 from the constancy of the ratio $k_i^{(1)}/(k_i^{(2)}/2!)$.

267

268

Table 2

269

270 Estimated parameters were also used to reconstruct the experimental $k_i^{(1)}$ and
271 $k_i^{(2)}$ values (see the continuous lines in Fig. 3). By using Eq. (4) to express the dependence
272 of $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}$ on the size class x_i with the estimates of their unknown parameters as
273 reported in Table 2 and substituting it into Eq. (3), an equation for the grinding kinetics
274 was obtained and allowed a good reconstruction of the Ri-vs.-t curves reported in Fig. 2.

275

276

Fig. 3

277

278

279

280

281 **3.2 Rheological properties**

282 Pastes withdrawn at different refining times exhibited a shear thinning behavior
283 (pseudoplastic), that is their apparent viscosity (η) was a decreasing function of the shear
284 rate ($\dot{\gamma}$), as shown in Fig. 4. Furthermore, at the lowest shear rate tested (0.011 s^{-1}) the

285 apparent viscosities differed greatly among the samples while at the highest shear rate
286 (70.90 s^{-1}) they tended to coincide and to be much smaller.

287

288 Fig. 4

289 As shown in Fig. 4, the experimental apparent viscosity data as a function of shear rate are
290 quite well described by the Casson model, the mean relative error between the
291 experimental and predicted data of each paste ranging from 3.6 to 7.7%. The model
292 parameters estimated by the weighted least squares method are reported in Table 3.

293

294 Table 3

295

296 While the yield stress increased remarkably as a function of time, η_{∞} seemed to
297 increase as well but to a much lesser extent. Both σ_0 and η_{∞} values are in line with the
298 values measured at 40°C reported by Taylor et al. (Taylor et al., 2009) for chocolate made
299 up of crumb (a dried mixture of milk powder, sugar and cocoa solids) and sunflower oil
300 (20 to 70 Pa and 4 to 15 Pa s, respectively) and dry mix milk, crumb, dark and white
301 chocolate (0.5 to 20 Pa and 1 to 10 Pa s, respectively).

302 The oil used to prepare the pastes as well as the supernatant liquid obtained by
303 centrifugation of the refined paste behaved as a Newtonian fluid (constant viscosity) in the
304 shear rate range of $0.89\text{-}89 \text{ s}^{-1}$ with viscosities of 42.0 ± 0.4 and $45.4\pm 3.0 \text{ mPa s}$,
305 respectively. It is worth noting that these viscosity values are coincident with the viscosity
306 of cocoa butter at 40°C which behaves as a Newtonian fluid with a viscosity of 45 mPa s
307 (Taylor et al., 2009). This allows to compare the rheological behavior at 30°C of the paste
308 under study with that of molten chocolate at 40°C .

309 To correlate the rheological properties of the pastes with their degree of refining, the
310 solid bed densities of the pastes were determined experimentally (Mongia, and Ziegler,
311 2000) and the values of ϕ_m were calculated through the algorithm developed by Lee (1970)
312 starting from the PSD of the pastes. Both ϕ_m and SBD decreased as a function of milling
313 time, from 0.759 to 0.716 and from 1145 to 1077 kg m^{-3} , respectively, with a similar trend.
314 This can be explained by considering that the PSD of the pastes becomes narrower as
315 milling proceeds, resulting in a decrease of the packing capability of the solids. Do et al.
316 (2007) studied the effect of PSD on the rheological properties of chocolate models

317 consisting of sugar and a cocoa butter equivalent. They simulated different PSDs by
318 mixing different proportions of sugar with two different solid sizes (fine and coarse). The
319 D_{90} of their dispersions varied between 27 (fine fraction) and 107 μm (coarse fraction) and
320 the ϕ_m that they estimated varied between 0.691 and 0.751, respectively. Based solely on
321 the D_{90} , the fine fraction of the abovementioned dispersions would correspond to the paste
322 under study refined for 60 min while the coarse one with the unrefined paste for which we
323 estimated values of ϕ_m of 0.724 and 0.789, respectively, thus very close to the ones
324 estimated by the cited authors.

325 There is a vast literature that relates ϕ_m to the viscosity of suspension systems and
326 shows that it is possible to optimize the PDS of a suspension to increase ϕ_m and thus
327 reduce the viscosity. This concept has been applied also to the case of chocolate (Bolenz et
328 al., 2014; Do et al., 2007). In the case of melted chocolate, efforts have been devoted to
329 optimizing the PSD, at a given volume fraction of solids, for example by mixing coarse
330 and fine solid particles, to increase ϕ_m and thus decreasing the viscosity of the product,
331 avoiding or limiting the addition of cocoa butter and viscosity modifiers (lecithin or other
332 emulsifiers). It is also known that excessive grinding of chocolate solid particles results in
333 viscosity increase and thus particle size distribution analysis is considered important to
334 control the grinding process in order to avoid overgrinding.

335 Eq. (7) does not show any explicit dependence of η on shear rate. One way to include
336 the shear dependence of suspension viscosity is to assume that ϕ_m changes with shear rate
337 as a result of microstructure modification, in particular agglomeration and deagglomeration
338 phenomena. For example, Wildemuth and Williams (1984) derived a relationship where ϕ_m
339 is a function of shear stress (σ) and monotonically increases from $\phi_{m,0}$ at $\sigma = 0$ to $\phi_{m,\infty}$ as σ
340 $\rightarrow \infty$. When substituted into an appropriate η_r versus ϕ/ϕ_m relationship, such as Eq. (7), the
341 result is a model that gives viscosity as a function of solid volume fraction and shear stress.
342 Windhab (2000), on the other hand, used the concept of fluid immobilization and applied
343 Eq. (7) by substituting the solid volume fraction ϕ with an effective solid volume fraction
344 that was expressed as a function of shear rate and other parameters.

345 We applied Eq. (7) to each couple of values of relative viscosity and corresponding
346 shear rate and estimated ϕ_m through a non-linear equation solver using a value of ϕ of
347 0.568 and $[\eta]=2.5$. As shear rate increased from 0.011 to 89.233 s^{-1} , ϕ_m increased from

348 0.570 to 0.588 or 0.569 to 0.583, respectively for the pastes refined for 15 or 120 min. The
349 geometric ϕ_m , estimated by the algorithm of Lee (1970) (Table 1), was equal to 0.759 and
350 0.716 for the pastes refined for 15 or 120 min, respectively. The disagreement between the
351 values of ϕ_m estimated by using Eq. (7), that is from rheological data, and those calculated
352 from the algorithm proves that the pastes under study were characterized by a high degree
353 of interaction that likely resulted in loose structures that immobilized a large part of the
354 fluid phase and that persisted even at the highest shear rates studied. In fact, if the particles
355 were fully dispersed and non interacting, by using Eq. (7) with $\phi_m = 0.716-0.759$ pertaining
356 to the PSD of pastes refined for 120-15 min, respectively, the relative viscosity of the
357 pastes can be calculated as 16.7-13.6, much smaller than the values presented by the
358 pastes, in the range of 145 to 52456. However, the relative viscosities at the highest shear
359 rate tested are closer to the prediction values than the relative viscosities at low shear rates.
360 So, it seems that at infinite share the relative viscosities tend to approach the values
361 predicted by Eq. (7). This is consistent with the idea that the viscosity of concentrated
362 suspensions is made up of two terms, hydrodynamic and structural viscosity (Lee, 1970).
363 The hydrodynamic viscosity is independent of the rate of shear and represents the limiting
364 viscosity at high rates of shear. On the other hand, the structural viscosity gives non-
365 Newtonian effects as a function of the rate of shear. Thus Eq. (7) represents only the
366 hydrodynamic viscosity. From these data, it seems that the effect of refining on the
367 rheological behavior is due more to the reduction of the particle diameter and thus to the
368 increase of the specific surface area of particles than to the reduction of the packing ability
369 of the particles. In fact, by increasing the specific surface of particles the interaction
370 between particles also increases and thus the probability of agglomerate formation
371 increases. Consequently, refining seems to influence more the structural viscosity than the
372 hydrodynamic viscosity.

373 Thus, it seems that the flow characteristics of the grinded pastes can be explained by the
374 theory of dense suspensions. Further studies are however necessary to develop a model for
375 the description of the rheological behavior as a function of solid packing fraction and shear
376 rate.

377

378 **4. Conclusions**

379 Modeling results show that the population balance approach described in the literature
380 in dry or wet grinding of non-food materials in various types of mills can be used
381 successfully to characterize the grinding process in a stirred ball mill of a food product
382 made up of several type of solids (cocoa, sugar, hazelnut) dispersed in a fat phase. The G-
383 H model was successfully used to describe the grinding kinetics of particles in each size
384 class. The first and second Kapur functions were well fitted with a four-parameter model
385 and allowed excellent reconstructions of the oversize (R_i) as a function of time (t) for each
386 size class.

387 The rheological properties of the grinded pastes were well described by the Casson
388 model. The increase of the apparent viscosity as a function of refining time can be only
389 partly explained by the decrease of the geometric solid packing fraction which affects the
390 hydrodynamics viscosity. Most likely, the system is characterized by a high degree of
391 particle interactions, that increases as the particle size reduces, thus increasing the
392 structural viscosity of the paste.

393

394 **Acknowledgments**

395

396 The authors thank MEC3-OPTIMA SRL (San Clemente, Italy) for supplying the
397 ingredients to prepare the hazelnut and cocoa based paste and Mr. Carlo Vanni (MEC3-
398 OPTIMA SRL) for his collaboration and useful discussions.

399 **Nomenclature**

400

401 *Symbols*

402 b_{ij} : breakage function of class sizes i and j

403 B_{ij} : cumulative breakage function of class i and j

404 D_i : diameter of particles in class size i (m)

405 D_{10}, D_{50}, D_{90} : 10th, 50th and 90th percentiles of PSD

406 f : paste fineness as measured by micrometer

407 $k_i^{(1)}$: first Kapur constant

408 $k_i^{(2)}$: second Kapur constant

409 k : empirical coefficient in Eq. (4) and (5)

410 m_i : mass of particles in class size i

411 R_i : cumulative weight fraction oversize x_i

412 S_i : selection function for class size i

413 t : time

414 x^* : empirical coefficient in Eq. (4)

415 X_i : volume fraction of particles in class size i

416

417 *Greek symbols*

418 α : empirical coefficient in Eq.s (4) and (5)

419 $(\phi_p)_j$: function predicting ϕ_m

420 $\dot{\gamma}$: shear rate

421 $[\eta]$: intrinsic viscosity, $\lim_{\phi \rightarrow 0} (\eta - \eta_s) / (\eta_s \phi)$

422 Λ : empirical coefficient in Eq. (4)

423 X_j : volume fraction of solid in size class i

424 η_∞ : viscosity at infinite shear rate, parameter in Eq. (6)

425 η : paste viscosity

426 η_r : paste reduced viscosity, η / η_s

427 η_s : dispersant viscosity

428 ρ_i : density of component i

429 σ_0 : yield stress, parameter in Eq. (6)

430 ϕ : volume fraction of solids in the paste

- 431 ϕ_{ij} : binary coefficients
- 432 ϕ_m : maximum packing volume fraction of the solids in the paste
- 433 $\phi_{\max}(D_i/D_j)$: maximum packing volume fraction of the solids in binary mixtures with
- 434 diameter ratio D_i/D_j .
- 435

436 **References**

- 437 Alamprese, C., Datei, L., Semeraro, Q., 2007. Optimization of processing parameters of a
438 ball mill refiner for chocolate. *J. Food Eng.* 83, 629–636.
439 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2007.04.014>
- 440 Armini V., Miele, N.A., Albero, M., Sacchi, R., Cavella, S., 2018, Formula optimization
441 approach for an alternative Ready-to-Use Therapeutic Food, *LWT - Food Science &*
442 *Technology*, 98, 148-153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2018.08.038>
- 443 Berlin, E., Pallansch, M.J., 1963. Influence of Drying Methods on Density and Porosity of
444 Milk Powder Granules. *J. Dairy Sci.* 46, 780–784. [https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.S0022-](https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.S0022-0302(63)89148-1)
445 [0302\(63\)89148-1](https://doi.org/10.3168/JDS.S0022-0302(63)89148-1)
- 446 Berthiaux, H., Varinot, C., Dodds, J., 1996, Approximate calculation of breakage
447 parameters from batch grinding tests, *Chemical Engineering Science*, 51, 4509–4516.
- 448 Birkett, J., 2009, Fat-based centres and fillings, Chapter In G Talbot (Ed.), *Science and*
449 *technology of enrobed and filled chocolate, confectionery and bakery products*, WP &
450 CRC Press, Cambridge, UK, 101-122.
- 451 Bolenz, S., Holm, M., Langkrär, C., 2014. Improving particle size distribution and flow
452 properties of milk chocolate produced by ball mill and blending. *Eur. Food Res.*
453 *Technol.* 238, 139–147. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-013-2094-7>
- 454 Do, T.A.L., Hargreaves, J.M., Wolf, B., Hort, J., Mitchell, J.R., 2007. Impact of particle
455 size distribution on rheological and textural properties of chocolate models with
456 reduced fat content. *J. Food Sci.* 72, 541–552. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-3841.2007.00572.x)
457 [3841.2007.00572.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-3841.2007.00572.x)
- 458 Fang, T., Zhang, H., Hsieh, T.T., Tiu, C., 1997. Rheological behavior of cocoa dispersions
459 with cocoa butter replacers. *J. Texture Stud.* 28, 11–26.
460 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-4603.1997.tb00099.x>
- 461 Fidaleo, M., Miele, N.A., Mainardi, S., Armini, V., Nardi, R., Cavella, S., 2017a, Effect of
462 refining degree on particle size, sensory & rheological characteristics of anhydrous
463 paste for ice creams produced in industrial stirred ball mill, *LWT - Food Science &*
464 *Technology*, 79, 242-250. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2017.01.046>
- 465 Fidaleo, M., Nardi, R., Mainardi, S., 2017b, Modeling the refining process of an anhydrous
466 hazelnut and cocoa paste in stirred ball mills, *Food and bioproducts processing*, 105,
467 147-156. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.fbp.2017.07.004>

468 Hennart, S.L.A., van Hee, P., Drouet, V., Domingues, M.C., Wildeboer, W.J., Meesters,
469 G.M.H., 2012. Characterization and modeling of a sub-micron milling process limited
470 by agglomeration phenomena, *Chemical Engineering Science*, 71, 484–495.

471 Kapur, P.C., Agarwal, P.K., 1970, Approximate solutions to the discretized batch grinding
472 equation, *Chemical Engineering Science*, 25, 1111–1113.

473 Lee, D.I., 1970. Packing of Spheres and its effects on the viscosity of suspensions. *J. Paint*
474 *Technol.* 42, 579–587.

475 Li, Q., Li, K., Ni, W., Li, D., Chen W., 2017, The Effect of Grinding Time on the
476 Performance of Gold Tailings Aerated Concrete, *Chemical Engineering Transactions*,
477 59, 349-354.

478 Lucisano, M., Casiraghi, E., Mariotti, M., 2006. Influence of formulation and processing
479 variables on ball mill refining of milk chocolate. *Eur. Food Res. Technol.* 223, 797–
480 802. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-006-0272-6>

481 McGear, R., 1961. Mechanical packing of spherical particles. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 44, 513–
482 522.

483 Miele, N.A., Di Monaco, R., Masi, P., Cavella, S., 2015, Reduced-calorie filling cream:
484 Formula optimization & mechanical characterization, *Chemical Engineering*
485 *Transactions*, 43, 67-72. <http://doi:10.3303/CET1543012>

486 Mongia, G., Ziegler, G.R., 2000, The Role of Particle Size Distribution of Suspended
487 Solids in Defining the Flow Properties of Milk Chocolate, *International Journal of Food*
488 *Properties*, 3, 137-147.

489 Ozdemir, F., Akinci, I., 2004. Physical and nutritional properties of four major commercial
490 Turkish hazelnut varieties. *J. Food Eng.* 63, 341–347.
491 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2003.08.006>

492 Purker, P., Agrawal, R., Kapur, P.C. 1986. A GH Scheme for Back-Calculation of
493 Breakage Rate Functions from Batch Grinding Data, *Powder Technology*, 45, 281–286.

494 Rao, M.A., 2007. Flow and functional models for rheological properties of fluid foods, in:
495 *Food Engineering Series*. pp. 27–58. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-70930-7_2

496 Servais, C., Jones, R., Roberts, I., 2002. The influence of particle size distribution on the
497 processing of food. *J. Food Eng.* 51, 201–208. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0260-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0260-8774(01)00056-5)
498 [8774\(01\)00056-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0260-8774(01)00056-5)

499 Taylor, J.E., Van Damme, I., Johns, M.L., Routh, A.F., Wilson, D.I., 2009. Shear

- 500 Rheology of Molten Crumb Chocolate. *J. Food Sci.* 74, E55–E61.
501 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-3841.2008.01041.x>
- 502 van der Vaart, K., Depypere, F., Graef, V. De, Schall, P., Fall, A., Bonn, D., Dewettinck,
503 K., 2013. Dark chocolate's compositional effects revealed by oscillatory rheology. *Eur.*
504 *Food Res. Technol.* 236, 931–942. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-013-1949-2>
- 505 Varinot, C., Berthiaux, H., Dodds, J., 1999, Prediction of the product size distribution in
506 associations of stirred bead mills, *Powder Technology*, 105, 228–236.
- 507 Wildemuth, C.R., Williams, M.C., 1984. Viscosity of suspensions modeled with a shear-
508 dependent maximum packing fraction. *Rheol. Acta* 23, 627–635.
509 <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01438803>
- 510 Windhab, E.J., 2000. Fluid immobilization-a structure-related key mechanism for the
511 viscous flow behavior of concentrated suspension systems. *Appl. Rheol.* 10, 134–144.

1 **Figure captions**

2 **Figure 1.** Particle size distribution of pastes at different grinding times: 0 (——),
 3 5 (----), 15 (---), 30 (———), 60 (---), 90 (—) and 120 ()-min.

4 **Figure 2.** Cumulative oversize fraction (R_i) as function of grinding time for different size
 5 classes (x_i): ■, 5.2 μm ; ●, 9.9 μm ; ▲, 16.4 μm ; □, 21.2 μm ; ○, 27.4 μm ; △, 35.3 μm ; x,
 6 45.6 μm . The points indicate the actual measurements while the continuous lines
 7 correspond to the model predictions obtained by Eq. (3) and Eq. (4) together with the
 8 parameter values reported in Table 2.

9 **Figure 3.** First ($k_i^{(1)}, \circ$) and second ($k_i^{(2)}, \square$) Kapur constants as a function of size class (x_i).
 10 Dots represent the constants estimated by fitting the experimental data with Eq. (3) applied
 11 to each size class while the continuous lines represent predictions by using Eq. (4) and the
 12 parameter estimates reported in Table 2.

13 **Figure 4.** Apparent viscosity (η) as a function of shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$) for pastes refined for 15
 14 (\square), 30 (\blacksquare), 60 (\circ), 90 (\bullet) and 120 (Δ) min. Symbols refer to experimental data while
 15 continuous lines to model predictions obtained by Eq. (6) together with the parameter
 16 values reported in Table 3.

17

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

1 **Tables**

2

3 **Table 1:** Fineness (f) and particle size distribution parameters (D_{10} , D_{50} , D_{90}) of pastes at
 4 different grinding times (mean \pm standard deviation).

Time (min)	f (μm)	D_{10} (μm)	D_{50} (μm)	D_{90} (μm)
0	118.67 \pm 1.85 ^a	2.67 \pm 0.02 ^a	13.72 \pm 0.29 ^a	95.45 \pm 2.75 ^a
5	87.33 \pm 2.40 ^b	2.67 \pm 0.03 ^a	12.72 \pm 0.11 ^b	71.84 \pm 1.02 ^b
15	56.00 \pm 3.21 ^c	2.31 \pm 0.07 ^b	10.12 \pm 0.22 ^c	46.82 \pm 0.43 ^c
30	34.33 \pm 0.88 ^d	2.24 \pm 0.02 ^b	8.75 \pm 0.06 ^d	33.42 \pm 0.41 ^d
60	23.33 \pm 0.66 ^e	2.012 \pm 0.007 ^c	7.12 \pm 0.01 ^e	22.42 \pm 0.09 ^e
90	17.33 \pm 0.88 ^f	1.795 \pm 0.002 ^d	6.246 \pm 0.006 ^f	18.20 \pm 0.04 ^f
120	16.67 \pm 0.33 ^f	1.644 \pm 0.002 ^e	5.751 \pm 0.005 ^g	16.32 \pm 0.07 ^g

5

6 **Table 2.** Point estimates of the unknown parameters of Eq. (4) obtained through nonlinear
 7 regression of the first and second Kapur constants, $k_i^{(1)}$ and $k_i^{(2)}$, as a function of x_i .

8

Parameter	Unit	$k_i^{(1)}$	$k_i^{(2)}$
k	$\text{min}^{-1} \mu\text{m}^{-\alpha}$ or $\text{min}^{-2} \mu\text{m}^{-\alpha}$	$-5.85 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.91 \cdot 10^{-6}$
α	Dimensionless	1.29	1.24
x^*	μm	96.28	94.16
Λ	Dimensionless	1.76	3.80
RMSE	min^{-1} or min^{-2}	$9.04 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.71 \cdot 10^{-6}$
DFE	Dimensionless	27	27

9

10 RMSE and DFE refer to the root mean square error of regression and its degrees of
 11 freedom, respectively.

12 **Table 3:** Rheological parameters of the Casson model (yield stress, σ_0 , and viscosity at
 13 infinite shear rate, η_∞), solid bed density (SDB) and maximum volume fraction (ϕ_{\max}) for
 14 pastes refined for different amounts of time.

Time (min)	η_∞ (Pa s)	σ_0 (Pa)	SBD (kg m^{-3})	ϕ_{\max} (-)
15	5.87± 0.21	10.98±0.31	1145±21	0.759
30	7.72±0.22	11.42± 0.28	1094±53	0.739
60	8.34±0.20	15.11±0.30	1088±3	0.724
90	8.14±0.17	20.59±0.31	1087	0.718
120	8.03± 0.15	25.42±0.33	1077	0.716

15 Data represent mean±standard error (for model parameters), mean±standard deviation (for
 16 replicated SBD measurements) or the algorithm estimated value (ϕ_{\max}).
 17